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THE CONCEPT OF "ROAD" IN MEDIEVAL ENGLISH LITERATURE

Abstract

The concept "road" as a multivalent symbol is widely encountered in world literature since ancient times and depending on the context is not always used in its direct meaning. However, in all cases the road is a metaphor of movement, change and progress. In literary works, the road mainly acts as a symbol of spiritual journey, efforts of self-discovery and new beginnings. In medieval English literature, the road as a multivalent concept representing both physical and symbolic journey symbolises the path to truth, enlightenment and salvation. This article examines philosophical, religious, spiritual and other aspects of the concept of "road" in the context of analysing two literary monuments of medieval English literature - the epic "Beowulf" and "The Canterbury Tales" by G. Chaucer. In the context of the characters' fates, the concept of the road is analysed as a multilayered symbol uniting the physical and spiritual dimensions of human existence.

Keywords: English Literature, "Beowulf", "The Canterbury Tales", Concept,

The road, as a universal archetype, is a constant and eternal image found in folklore and literary works. M. M. Bakhtin, highlighting the chronotope of the "road" as one of the key narrative and meaning-creating chronotopes, argues that "few works are without variations of the motif of the road". M. M. Bakhtin writes: "On the road ('the great road'), the spatial and temporal paths of the most diverse people—representatives of all estates, conditions, religions, nationalities, and ages—intersect at one point in time and space" (Бахтин, 1975).

One of the literary works in which the concept of "road" manifests on various levels is the poem *Beowulf*, a striking example of the Old English epic tradition. (Heaney). Ernest J.B. Kirtlan writes: "Beowulf" may rightly be pronounced the great national epic of the Anglo-Saxon race. Not that it exalts the race so much as that it presents the spirit of the Anglo-Saxon peoples, the ideals and aims, the manners and customs, of our ancestors, and that it does so in setting before us a great national hero" (Kirtlan, 2015). The concept of "road" here can be interpreted from several perspectives. The protagonist, Beowulf, embarks on both literal and metaphorical journeys, during which his courage, moral integrity, and leadership qualities are tested. In the poem, the heroes must traverse various "roads": from the "dark" seas to the challenges of battling terrifying enemies. These roads hold both physical and symbolic significance, relating to fate or personal choice.

The first visible level in the poem is the physical one. Beowulf's journey to Denmark to aid King Hrothgar is the first significant "road" in the poem. This sea voyage is fraught with danger and demonstrates Beowulf's courage and determination. It is a physical transition into a foreign land, but also an introduction to a world of trials, where Beowulf will prove his worth by facing Grendel's mother and, ultimately, the dragon.

The concept of "road" is also reflected in the scenes of battles with sea monsters and the epic combat episodes. Beowulf's confrontations with these dangers

are both literal and figurative expressions of his heroism. All of this signifies Beowulf's noble journey, with each physical step he takes bringing him closer to fulfilling his destined heroic mission.

This, in turn, leads to the analysis of another aspect of the concept of the road: the theme of the road as fate. The road of fate, linking physical paths, represents a journey that Beowulf cannot control. The plot of the poem suggests that although individuals make choices, they remain subject to forces beyond their control. The road of fate is evident throughout the work, especially in the moments leading to the demise of the main characters.

For example, Beowulf's final battle with the dragon can be seen as the culmination of fate. Despite his previous victories, this battle marks the end of his journey. The poem reflects how Beowulf confronts the consequences of his past actions in the latter part of his life. His fate, defined by his courage, remains unavoidable. The dragon, symbolizing Beowulf's past deeds and accumulated wealth, also serves as a harbinger of his ultimate demise. The "road" of fate in *Beowulf* suggests that even the greatest heroes are not immune to the inevitable flow of time and death.

The next aspect of the concept of "road" in *Beowulf* is tied to moral and ethical values. Beowulf's decisions are guided by a code of honor that reflects the values of Anglo-Saxon warrior culture. These values are evident in his willingness to fight dangerous enemies to protect his people and his reputation, rather than for personal gain. Throughout the narrative, Beowulf chooses the "right" path, adhering to virtues such as loyalty, courage, and generosity.

In the first part of the poem, Beowulf chooses to fight Grendel without weapons. This act is a testament to his honor. He prefers to face the creature on equal terms, adhering to the warrior code that values personal strength and bravery over reliance on external factors and tricks. Similarly, Hrothgar's decision to fight Grendel's mother after the death of his beloved queen

demonstrates his sense of duty and moral responsibility.

Beowulf's journey also represents a "path" of leadership. As a young hero, he seeks glory through strength and martial prowess, but as an aging king, he comes to understand the importance of wisdom and responsibility. His final confrontation with the dragon illustrates how his "path" of leadership has evolved. He no longer seeks personal glory; instead, he is concerned with the safety of his people and the legacy he will leave behind. The "path" of leadership in *Beowulf* emphasizes the transformation of a warrior, who once sought personal fame, into a king focused on the welfare of his kingdom.

In the Middle Ages, the idea of "the road" was closely intertwined with religious, moral, and social themes. Whether it concerned a physical journey, a moral choice, or a spiritual pilgrimage, it was a central concept for understanding the human condition, the fate of the soul, and the relationship between man, God, and society. The hero's journey along these paths often symbolized his inner development and ultimate destiny.

examines the monomyth of the "hero's journey" in the context of the road and journey, concluding that it is ultimately and "a wonderful transition and return".

Pilgrimages and various religious-spiritual journeys were common phenomena, as people undertook them for spiritual reasons. The concept of "the road" became fundamental in religious literature, such as pilgrimages to God or salvation. According to I.F. Golovchenko, "the concept of journey in the Middle Ages was also perceived through the lens of religion: the journey had an allegorical nature and was primarily seen as a path toward something unattainable" (Головченко, 2017).

A striking example of this is Geoffrey Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales*, in which the pilgrimage to Canterbury serves as both a physical journey and a metaphor for the search for the salvation of the soul (Chaucer, 2019). The frequent use of the road as a metaphor can be explained by the fact that "the connection between time and space in the depiction of the road generates rich metaphors" (Мальцева, 2022). Here, the concept of the passage of time is expressed through metaphors such as "life's journey," "historical path," "laborious path," and others.

The physical journey undertaken by the pilgrims also symbolizes the spiritual, moral, and social paths they choose. "Thus, the road is connected with movement, which can be both physical and spiritual, i.e., actual and mental" (Бондарь, 2006). Chaucer employs the concept of the "road" to explore human nature, social roles, and the relationship between fate and free will. It is this concept that plays a central role in understanding the structure and meaning of the work. An analysis of Chaucer's tales reveals that the concept of the "road" served as a foundation through which broader themes such as morality, pilgrimage, and social mobility in medieval society could be explored.

The literal journey of the pilgrims from London to Canterbury is a shared experience, but it is also marked

by individual stories and experiences. The pilgrims represent all layers of medieval English society: among them are a knight, a monk, a priest, a doctor, a sailor, a merchant, a weaver, a cook, a yeoman, a canon, and others. Their stories are quite diverse. Each of these characters has their own lifestyle, which influences their narrative, actions, and attitude toward the pilgrimage.

The physical "road" for Chaucer serves as a means to represent the intersection of medieval society with the pilgrims, ranging from knights to the clergy and commoners. For instance, in the *Knight's Tale*, the ideal medieval "path" of knighthood and valor is embodied. The medieval person was convinced of their powerlessness in the face of the cruelty of gods or fate, who seemed to revel in human suffering. However, the dying Arcite refutes the notion of humans as mere toys of fate, finding the strength to overcome fate's will, reconcile with Palamon, and return to the knightly ideals of "selfless nobility, true justice, and self-forgetting service to others." The subsequent wedding of Palamon and Emily, following Arcite's death, for medieval readers, affirmed that "the will of the all-good God, turning all things to good," acted, "though in a hidden form, even in pagan antiquity." "When the great first-moving Cause had created the fair chain of love, great was the deed and high his intent, and well wist he what he did" (Chaucer, 1919).

Chaucer presents characters who, on one hand, submit to divine will and the natural order, while on the other hand, possess the autonomy to choose their own actions. The conflict between Palamon and Arcite in the *Knight's Tale* can be interpreted as a struggle between fate and free will. Both men believe they desire to marry the same woman, yet their actions, based on free will, lead them down a path that ultimately ends in tragedy. This reflects the medieval belief in divine intervention, while also acknowledging the significance of human choice.

Each of the characters in the poem seeks their own path, and the "path" of the Wife of Bath reflects a more secular, experience-based understanding of love and marriage (Chaucer, 1919). The Wife of Bath's story tells of her journey to independence and control over her life. Her multiple marriages are part of her "path" toward personal empowerment, challenging the social expectations placed on women in Chaucer's time. The "Monk's Tale" presents a "path" of piety and humility, preaching repentance and moral righteousness. Through these contrasting "paths," Chaucer explores how social status, gender, and personal experience shape individuals' approaches to life and pilgrimage (Chaucer, 1919).

Thus, the tale of each pilgrim can be seen as a description of their personal moral or spiritual journey. Chaucer reflects the diversity of lifestyles, illustrating the contradiction between virtue and vice, divine will and human will, as well as the consequences of different life choices. Abdullayeva, who studies the same problem in English literature, writes that in this case the "the sharp contradiction between the moral values and the values created by religious law is captured in the mockery of bitter laughter" (Abdullayeva, 2021).

In conclusion, it can be argued that in *Beowulf*, the concept of "the road" operates on multiple levels, revealing profound symbolic layers of heroism, fate, and morality. Whether it is the inevitable journey across the seas, determined by fate, or the moral choices that define the hero's character, the "road" plays a powerful symbolic role in the poem. *Beowulf*'s journey teaches that the choice of path is, on one hand, linked to the decisions of the individual, and on the other, to forces beyond his control. In this sense, *Beowulf* is not only the heroic story of one man but also the tale of the complex interaction between choice, fate, and the course of life.

In "The Canterbury Tales", Geoffrey Chaucer masterfully combines the literal and metaphorical use of the concept of "the road" to explore themes of morality, social structure, and spiritual development. The concept of "the road" serves both as the foundation for physical pilgrimage and as a means for a deeper exploration of the characters' inner lives. By examining how people from different social strata travel their personal paths, Chaucer invites readers to reflect on the complexity of the human experience and the paths they choose in life.

Conclusion. In medieval literature, the concept of the road is deeply interwoven with themes of morality, spirituality, and social structure. Geoffrey Chaucer's "The Canterbury Tales" epitomizes this with its pilgrimage framework, where the literal journey to Canterbury mirrors the characters' moral and spiritual quests. The diversity of pilgrims—from knights to commoners—reflects the intersection of social strata, while their individual stories explore universal themes of virtue, redemption, and human folly.

Similarly, in the Old English epic "Beowulf", the road signifies both physical and existential journeys. *Beowulf*'s travels, fraught with trials and battles, symbolize his path to heroism, self-discovery, and eventual

mortality. The interplay between fate and free will is central to the narrative, as *Beowulf* navigates the challenges posed by his destiny.

References

1. Бахтин М.М. (1975). Формы времени и хронотопа в романе. Очерки по исторической поэтике <https://yanko.lib.ru/books/cultur/bahtin-hronotop.htm>
2. Бондарь Н.Ю. (2006). Своеобразие архетипа дороги в романе Дж. Барнса "История мира в 10 1/2 главах" // Літературознавчий збірник. №26-27. с.10
3. Головченко И.Ф. (2017). Литературное путешествие в эпоху античности и Средневековья: конвергенция типологических особенностей. Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики, Тамбов, Грамота, №3(69): в 3-х ч. Ч.1. с.15-17.
4. Мальцева Е.А. (2022). Дорога как предмет концептуальной рефлексии // Идеи и идеалы. Е.14, № 3, ч.2., с.392
5. Abdullayeva, Y. (2021). Historical Imagination: Interpretation of the Past in Postmodern Novels A History of the World in 10½ Chapters and The Incomplete Manuscript. Academic Journal of Modern Philology, (14), 9-24.
6. Chaucer G. (1919). The Canterbury tales, New-York, Duffield Company, p. 63-64. <https://archive.org/details/canterburytaleso00chauoft/page/62/mode/2up>
7. Chaucer G. The Canterbury tales. The Wife of Bath's Prologue and Tale. <https://www.poetryintranslation.com/>
8. Heaney S. *Beowulf*. A new verse translation. <http://www.somanybooks.org/eng205/Beowulf.pdf>
9. Kirtlan E.J.B. (2015). The story of *Beowulf*. New York Thomas Y. Crowell Company Publisher, p. 7. <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/50742/50742-h/50742-h.htm>